

MGNREGA: A Tool for Social Equality

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, *Abstract:*

MGNREGA as a comprehensive envelop cover to unemployed and underemployed rural poor in gainful employment opportunities brings transformation in socio-economic conditions of people. If implemented effectively, rural India would progress by leaps and bound. Its impact can be noticed in reduction of distress migration and increasing trend in quality of life.

Introduction

The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) 2005 is a right based demand driven and employment providing act aiming transforming the life course of rural poor. The employment is generated through the creation of assets that helps rural poor. The act endorses employment as an entitlement and entrusted with obligation to provide 100 days of employment at fixed wage rate to all rural people whose members wish to do unskilled manual works. The implication of MGNREGA in improving the socio-economic status of rural households has been successively felt. The impact can be noticed in the reduction of distress migration, gradual progress in bridging the gap between income & expenditure over and above a substantial improvement of socio-economic conditions of the rural work force. There are nine types of prescribed works with descriptive detail in the bracket under MGNREGA, namely water conservation and harvesting (digging new tanks/ponds, small check dams, etc), draught proofing and plantation (afforestation, tree plantation, etc), flood control and protection (drainage in water logged areas, construction and repair of embankment, etc), land development (plantation, land leveling, etc), micro irrigation works (Minor irrigation canals, etc), renovation of traditional water bodies (desilting tanks / ponds, desilting of old canals, desilting of traditional open wells, etc), irrigation facility on land (Scheduled caste and schedule tribes, rural poor of land reform, etc), rural connectivity (Construction of roads, etc) and others, as and when required¹.

The asset creation works through MGNREGA tends to enable rural poor to engage in gainful employment and allows combat distress migration, if not addressed, inflicting on a number of jeopardized social situations. Obviously, the distantly social relations have so many thresholds where the absence of togetherness adversely influences the community life, in general and family life, in particular. The community has to leave many invaluable units, and a family suffers from the absence of effective individual support. Though migration incentivizes higher incomes for households, where men are centrally employed as workers, such entitlements lag behind due to obvious extremity of subordination

¹ Retrieved from <http://nrega.nic.in> on 4.10.2017

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issues. Casteism, xenophobia and cloud judgments are some of the effects of migration which impose a higher degree of duress and risks on the attendants. The employment opportunities through MGNREGA are also made available to old age people. Those who cannot get employment elsewhere, MGNREGA provides opportunities. Thus, MGNREGA in that context proves to be blind man's stick. It does not only give only employment, but through engagement brings social cohesion and integration.

Nevertheless, the two fold objectives of the asset creations are to aim at addressing the 'principal causes of hunger and starvation in rural areas, by ensuring that poor can expect to earn a living wage without compromising their dignity and demand work as their right'². The programme has the potential to lead the economy in labor intensive growth path through the asset creation works. Though the positive results have been lost in the backdrop of critical reports and anti-MGNREGA campaigns, the significant outcome of the implementation cannot be squarely ruled out considering the efficacy of created assets, at all India basis. Varied in degree and intensity, the asset creation works have rolled on paving the productions and meaningful path for the rural poor. Subsequently, women have earned benefits through putting themselves to worksites. This has helped them to evolve with a sense of negotiation and bargaining power at household level in terms of their decision making, probable expenditure items and over and above their denied say to be now recognized beyond the four walls, as spotted through their existing condition, where independence in collection and spending of MGNREGA wages, brings greater degree of say in decision making within and beyond the household. This is an upward mobility triggered on bringing desirable changes resulting in judicious allocation of resources. Thus, MGNREGA positively influences both men and women in rural pockets with abject poverty.

MGNREGA and Migration

The relationship between MGNREGA and migration can be spelled out in terms of income, landholding size, herd size and other important assets of households. The income and employment security, migration, debt repayment, extent of participation in MGNREGA works and socio-economic status of rural poor determine the mode and conduction of migration. The fact that the gap between the income of rural and urban India has been estimated. 'The per capita Net Value Added (NVA) for 2011-12 at current basic prices (base year 2011-12) is Rs. 101313/- for the urban areas and Rs. 40772 for the rural

² Mishra, SK (2011). Asset Creation Under MGNREGA: A Study in three Districts in Madhya Pradesh, IMJ, Vol. 3, Issue 3, Indore.

areas³. In this regard, 'the under current is the rural income would be doubled by 2022'⁴. Though the upkeep of rural infrastructure has been given a prime concern by the governments since long time back, the fruit of it is yet to be harnessed by the rural India. This may also tend to check migration and trigger unbridled initiation of rural development projects, particularly agriculture.

However, seasonal migration among rural laborers is found significant. Rural households in India use migrant labor offered by their members to improve well-being by both reducing the impacts of inferior conditions and by raising household income levels. 'Migrant labourers act as compensating mechanism used by households to lessen their disadvantageous position. Migrant households often tend to display lower education level, lower levels of income from agriculture, and an inferior geographical location'⁵. Side by side, extreme dependence on agriculture, poverty, lower incidence of welfare outreach and unbridled crime are the general concerns attributed to rural outmigration. However, the deficiencies in reproducible tangible capital related to labour in the face of high incidence in population density exacerbates mostly the available opportunities thereby increasing rural underemployment fostering migration as an apt solace. Thus, urban sites become magnet for migration accommodating rural people with poverty. This gives rise to 'urbanization of poverty'⁶. In this context, asset creation works under MGNREGA help the prospective migrants look back at their own available resource base. This helps to wagers to stay back and create a more meaningful and productive life within their own social boundary.

MGNREGA, Income and Expenditure

Moreover, rural households earn their incomes from varied sources, consisting of cultivation of livestock, agricultural wage labourer, and other non-farm employment opportunities. Mostly, rural households earn their livelihood through non-farm activities, casual labour, migration to other rural-urban areas and wage based activities. In the absence of the absence of these, one is confronted with a dilemma of 'living in' and 'coping with'. 'In order to mitigate risk, land constraints, responsiveness to crisis as push factors and complementarities with existing income activities, higher profitability of activities deployed as pull factors, necessary steps are to be taken. These are largely governed and regulated by factors, such as education skills, caste religion, asset ownership, household size, and credit availability does influence the decision of rural household to participate and also decide on extent of

³ The Times of India (2016). Big Gap in Per Capita Income in Urban and Rural Areas, The Times of India, City, Delhi, May 10, 2016.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Haberfeld, Y. et al (1999). Seasonal migration rural labour in India, Population Research and Policy Review 19: 473-489, Kulwar Academic Publishers, Netherland

⁶ Harris and Todaro (1970). Migration, Unemployment and Development: A Two-Sector Analysis, The American Economic Review, Vol. 60, No. 1, American Economic Association, USA.

participation in a particular non-farm activities⁷. Since the rural India is marked by uneven distribution of land holdings, the difference in income level is bound to widen. This difference becomes acute when contrasted with very low income wagers. Thus, either they migrate for jobs outside their household or take recourse to MGNREGA's job opportunities.

Nevertheless, change in the consumption pattern and purchase behavior of households durables among employment rural poor due to MGNREGA portal, effectiveness has been noticed while conducting a study "Perception of Users, Quality and Durability of Assets Created Under MGNREGA: A study of Four Districts in Bihar". Though derived from the Bihar's wagers' experience, the application and negotiation are not much of difference.

MGNREGA Wages

A study commissioned in four districts of Bihar namely, Nalanda and Jehanabad (good performing) and Madhubani and Paschim Champaran (poorly performing) throw light on the expenditure pattern of wages earned through MGNREGA.

The chart below shows the expenditure pattern due to wages earned through MGNREGA on various heads viz. food items, farming, children education, health, house repair, loan repayment. This does not capture the quantum of amount spent on each head, but it shows as to how wages are spent by items.

Figure 1: Expenditure trend of MGNREGA Wages (%)

⁷ Chadha, GK (2002). Rural-Non Farm Employment in India: What does recent experience teach us?, The Indian Journal of Labour Economics, 45, No. 4, The Indian Society of Labour Economics, New Delhi.

Source: Primary Information⁸

It was found that on an average 72% of respondents spent their MGNREGA wages on food items. In Paschim Champaran 78% reported it followed by Madhubani (76%), Nalanda (71%) and Jehanabad (64%). It was discovered in the same study that 62% of them spent their MGNREGA wages on farming. This was maximum in Nalanda (58%) followed by Jehanabad (38%), Paschim Champaran (34%) and Madhubani (21%).

It appeared in the study that MGNREGA has helped educational pursuits. 59% of the respondents said that they spent their MGNREGA wages on their children education where Madhubani cloaked highest by 79%, followed by each Paschim Champaran and Jehanabad (63%) and Nalanda (32%). It was found that 31% of the respondents spend their MGNREGA wages on health.

It may be derived from the trend that 91% respondents spent their wages on house repair with maximum (96%) in Pashim Chamaparn followed by 91% each in Madhubani, Jehanabad and (87%) Nalanda. Wages earned were also spent for loan repayment.

Benefits of Created Assets under MGNREGS

MGNREGS is one of the biggest livelihood and social security ensuring programmes in the world. This is to be considered as a spine of the rural development in India. MGNREGS has benefitted to the community as well as individuals at all levels. Considering the socio-economic benefits, durable assets have brought benefits immensely. The acceptance to benefits has been recognized by different policy assessing agencies. The benefits can be seen while analyzing the MGNREGS improved purchasing power of the poor and there is calculable evidence that the rural poor now enjoy more consumable items than ever before. They have started sending their children to schools. The women have started participating in decisions and the trend has grown if we look at the position of census 2011 and the collected primary information of 2017 during the study. In fact, the MGNREGA works has turned as a boon for the people who are mostly farmers and agriculture laborers depending exclusively on agriculture produce. Nevertheless, MGNREGA signifies a huge step forward in asset generation mechanism with local workforce and emboldening social security mechanism for the rural poor.

Created assets under the MGNREGA scheme have multifaceted benefits at both individual and the community levels for the rural poor. Since its launch in the year 2005, in three phases, Phase I (from 2nd February 2006), Phase II (2007-2008) and Phase III (from 1st April, 2008), the focus of MGNREGA has centripetally been in augmenting wage employment for the rural poor. One of the main components that have been gradually gained significance in the scheme is its ability to support natural resource management through asset creation works that address chronic poverty, recurring droughts, floods, water management over and above, and sustainable development at the local level. In this process, the Act has codified different types of works to be undertaken using the guaranteed employment strategies. Currently out of 14 focus areas under the Act, the larger attentions have been attributed to water and soil conversation. In case of Bihar, it has been on the works related to rural connectivity. It has been actively carried out in four sampled districts of our study area. If we look closely at the nature and type of different works and its associated benefits to the people at the individual and community levels then the

⁸ Findings from study, "Perception of Users, Quality and Durability of Assets Created under MGNREGA: A Study of Four Districts in Bihar", IIPA, September, 2017.

Figure 17 shown below represents the trend of the benefits by creation of different assets in the four districts of our study area.

The benefits of the assets creation works under MGNREGA, Nalanda district represents that out of the total samples, 100% reported that they have benefited by check-dam works undertaken in their villages, 94.16% rural poor claimed that the migration has relatively been reduced by virtue of the availability of employment opportunities in nearby locations and settings.

Table 1: Perceived benefits of Created Assets under MGNREGA (%)

Districts Options/Responses	Nalanda		Jehanabad		Madhubani		Paschim Champanan		All districts total	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
No benefit at family level	1	99	33	67	5	95	10	90	12	88
Economic benefits	82	18	62	38	68	32	65	35	69	31
Village level benefits	69	31	58	42	30	70	42	58	50	50
Individual employment benefits	75	25	78	22	20	80	68	32	60	40
Reduced Migration levels	83	17	65	35	71	29	70	30	72	28
Increased irrigation facility	84	16	69	31	57	43	46	54	64	36
IHHL	70	30	63	37	74	26	82	18	72	28
Check dam	82	18	51	49	37	63	29	71	50	50
Rural connectivity	88	12	89	11	81	19	95	5	88	12
No Change	5	95	22	78	34	66	32	68	23	77

Source: Primary Information⁹

There are unique opportunities for the rural poor corresponding to proven appreciation by the rural poor, particularly the underprivileged and disadvantaged sections of the rural pockets. Some of them hoped that MGNREGA would enable them to avoid long distance seasonal migration, with all its hardship.

The findings of the study clearly indicate that MGNREGA is an efficient and effective strategy of the rural development. The rural poor of Bihar in the four selected districts have largely been benefited. The individual and community assets creations are the eye-catching features of the MGNREGA operation. It has brought about changes in socio-economic conditions of the rural poor. The pace with which the schemes operate, require more accountability and transparency. The respondents find the schemes very effective provided they get the wage rate in line with market rates. The individual assets planned and executed require completion at the earliest to be able to be used by the rural poor. The assets created require maintenance for which effective convergence with other scheme may be ensured.

Selection, organization and interpretation are the three effective stages involved in perception building. Following the idea, right kind of assets to be created, scanned through Panchayat level meetings, needs to be brought in. To ensure organizational effectiveness, mandatory interactive meetings on monthly basis should be organized. The meeting should discuss all concerning areas, viz. the kinds of works to be undertaken, how it is to be executed and integration with local resource base. If these issues are put together and discussed, obviously the interpretation would go in the desired direction and people will benefit at great deal.

Improvement in the Socio-Economic Conditions from MGNREA Works

⁹ Ibid

To improve the socio-economic conditions of the rural poor, MGNREGA wages play key role. In fact improved socio-economic status brings happiness in one's life course. Socio-economic status is the regulating conditions on which one finds the mode and conduction of the life course. It also carves out the inherent continuity in setbacks and success. Therefore, socio-economic conditions maps out the obvious direction in effective steps are to be taken up. It was found from the sample size of 480 respondents that 385 of them confirmed that their socio-economic status was improved, while 95 rural poor reported nothing much was changed.

The study revealed that the change in socio-economic condition of the rural poor is largely fueled by MGNREGA wages. The wagers experience boredom; fatigue and several undiagnosed health issues, as the single day of absence may give adverse ripple effect on their survival. It has also been reported by many of the rural poor that though the socio-economic conditions have been improving gradually, fastening the rate of improvement through developmental initiatives need to be integrated with the scheme. A multiple scheme, multiagency and multi-benefit approach can be a fruitful idea for activating hands in vocational engagements. Convergence of MGNREGA with other scheme of public works can potentially improve the skill levels among the workers and reduce the degree of their vulnerability. Also, the incorporation of some special provisions for the elderly persons within the MGNREGA is an immediate need to mitigate the problems being faced by the old persons who find it difficult to do the hard physical labor.

The table given below clearly reflects that out of the four districts, on an average 96% people reported that the MGNREGA has improved their socio-economic condition while 4 % beneficiaries on an average reported that nothing much has improved in their socio-economic conditions even after long association with the scheme.

Figure 2: Improvement in the Socio-Economic Conditions of MGNREGA Works

Source: Primary Information¹⁰

¹⁰ Ibid

The maximum benefit of the scheme in connection with the socio-economic conditions was observed with the respondents of Jehanabad and Nalanda the districts. Lower intensity was received in West Champaran and Nalanda districts. The reasons assigned by respondents are not being benefitted by MGNREGA are: unavailability of timely work, inhuman behavior by MGNREGA officials, physical unfitness, and several other unmitigated challenges.

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